

**PHARMACOEPIDEMOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF THE PERFORMED
CONSERVATIVE TREATMENT IN PATIENTS WITH
CHOLELITHIASIS OF THE GERONTOLOGICAL GROUP OF
NAMANGAN**

**Mamasaliev N.S.
Salakhidinov S.Z.
Mamasaliev Z.N.
Usmonov B.U.
Qurbonova R.R.**

**Andijan State Medical Institute, Uzbekistan
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15130902>**

Relevance. According to the WHO, in the modern treatment and diagnostic process of cholelithiasis (CSD) it is important, especially in individuals of the gerontological group (75-90 years and above), not only to provide scientific information on a certain type of treatment (surgical or conservative) and clinical and fundamental recommendations, but also to acquire modern innovative technologies acceptable for preventive surgery and the ability to use them. For the advanced development of CSD surgery in the 21st century, it is important to identify the most susceptible individuals with high or very high risk for this pathology and their special prevention to ensure the process of early detection, effective and safe treatment (with proper pharmacovigilance, pharmacoepidemiological screening) and the prevention of not only CSD itself, but also formidable complications of cholecystectomy, cholecystostomy, choledochotomy, choledochomyotomy and transduodenal sphincteropylotomy.

The aim of the study is to study the prevalence, pharmacoepidemiology of cholelithiasis and its main risk factors among the male and female unorganized population of the gerontological group of the Fergana Valley to enable scientifically based planning and optimization of early diagnosis, prevention and treatment of this disease.

The object of the study was a contingent of 4,500 individuals of the gerontological age population, formed using random number tables based on the nominal electoral lists of men and women in three regions of the Fergana Valley; as well as 779 patients with cholelithiasis who were undergoing inpatient treatment in the regional multidisciplinary hospitals of Andijan, Namangan and Fergana (for VEN analysis).

The subject of the study: were the results of general clinical and biochemical blood tests, survey, physical, instrumental and

pharmacoepidemiological monitoring; as well as the method of "daily nutrition reproduction" adapted to the peculiarities of Uzbek cuisine.

Research methods. To solve the set tasks, epidemiological, clinical, laboratory, biochemical, instrumental, pharmacoepidemiological and statistical research methods were used, as well as the "daily nutrition reproduction" method.

Results of the study: results of the pharmacoepidemiological study of cholelithiasis in individuals of the gerontological group of Namangan. Pharmacoepidemiological analysis of the performed conservative treatment of cholelithiasis was carried out in 180 patients; the gerontological group of women consisted of 151 people (20.1%) and men - 189 people (79.9%) ($\chi^2=135.1$; $P<0.001$; $RR=0.252$; $95\% CI=0.188-0.337$). 9 types of conservative therapy are used; its individual types among the general gerontological group, the group of men and women of Namangan with cholelithiasis were used with the following frequency of use: 1) antihypertensive drugs - 1.06%, 6.3% and 7.4%, respectively ($\chi^2 = 0.478$; $P > 0.05$; $RR = 0.700$; $95\% CI = 0.225-21.79$); 2) antispasmodics - 2.65%, 11.1% and 13.8% ($\chi^2 = 19.69$; $P < 0.001$; $RR = 0.238$; $95\% CI = 0.106-0.535$); 3) analgesics - 2.65%, 11.1% and 13.8% ($\chi^2=19.69$; $P<0.001$; $RR=0.238$; $95\% CI=0.106-0.535$); 4) antibacterial drugs - 2.65%, 11.1% and 13.8% ($\chi^2=19.69$; $P<0.001$; $RR=0.238$; $95\% CI=0.106-0.535$); 5) enzyme inhibitors - 2.65%, 11.1% and 13.8% ($\chi^2=19.69$; $P<0.001$; $RR=0.238$; $95\% CI=0.106-0.535$). 6) infusion agents - 2.65%, 11.1%, and 13.8% ($\chi^2=19.69$; $P<0.001$; $RR=0.238$; $95\% CI=0.106-0.535$); 7) NSAIDs - 2.12%, 3.2%, and 5.3% ($\chi^2=4.513$; $P<0.05$; $RR=2.800$; $95\% CI=1.251-6.268$); 8) anticoagulants - 2.65%, 11.1%, and 13.8% ($\chi^2=19.69$; $P<0.001$; $RR=0.238$; $95\% CI=0.106-0.535$); 9) proton inhibitors - 1.06%, 3.7% and 4.8% ($\chi^2=0.079$; $P>0.05$; $RR=1.200$; $95\% CI=0.350-4.114$).

References:

1. Буеверов А.О. Клинико – патологические параллели неалкогольной жировой болезни печени и желчно каменной болезни//Росс журн гастроэнтерол гепатом колопроктол. – 2019; 29 (1). – С. 17 – 21.
2. Гальперин Э.И. Механическая желтуха: состоянии "мнимой стабильности", последствие "второго удара", принципа лечения//Анмалы хирургической гепатологии. – 2011. – 16(3): 17 – 24.
3. Драпкина О.М. Неалкогольная жировая болезнь печени: не закрытие терапевтические нельзя//В кн:VII Международный интернет конгресс специалистов по внутренним болезням. – Москва. – VI DOX. – 2018. – С. 13 – 14.

4. Ермолов А.С., Дасаев М.А. Юргенко С.В. Диагностика и лечение холангиолитиаза после холецистэктомии//Хирургия – 2002 - №4. – С. 6 – 9.
5. Иваткин В.Т., Маев И.В. и др. Рекомендации Российской гастроэнтерологической ассоциации по диагностике и лечению желчнокаменной болезни//РЖГГК, 2016. - №3. – С. 64 – 80.
6. Королев М.П., Федотов Л.Е., Аванесян Р.Г., и др. Холедохолитиаз, имитирующий первичный склерозирующий холангит//”Вестник хирургии”. – 2017. - № 4. С – 93.
7. Онещенко С.В., Дарвин В.В. Профилактика послеоперационных осложнений в хирургии описторхозногопоражения желчевыводящих путей. //Анналы хирургической гепатологии. – 2017. – ТОМ 22 - №4 – С. 66.
8. Павлов И.А. Оптимизация лечебной тактики при остром холецистите у больных пожилого и старческого возраста//ДИС...канд.мед.наук. – М - . 2002. – С. 170.
9. Рыбачков В.В. Механическая желтуха//Ярославль – Изд.дом. ЯГТУ. – 2015 – С. 196 – 198.
10. Aymerich R.R., Prakaash C. et al. Sphincter of oddi manometry: is it necessary to measure both biliary and pancreatic sphincter pressures?//Gastrointest Endosc – 2000: 52 (2): 184 – 185.
11. Festi D, Dormi A. et al. Incidence of gallstone disease in Italy: results from a multicenter, population – based Italian study (the MICOL project)//World J Gastroenterol. – 2008: 14(34): 5283 – 5286.
12. Hughes B.B. et al. Projections of global health out comes from 2005 to 2060 using the International Futures integ. Fore casting model. Bull worid. Helth Organ. 2011;89:479 – 484.
13. <https://www.un.org/en/sections>.
14. Jaunoo SS. et al. Post cholecystectomy syndrome (PCS).//Int S Surg. 2010: 8(1):16.